

Role of information and communication technologies and innovations in the field of vocational education

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Abstract. In the contemporary educational milieu, the integration of innovative technologies serves as a catalyst for a paradigm shift, fostering an environment that is dynamic, engaging, and responsive to the evolving needs of students. The symbiotic relationship between tradition and innovation is envisaged not as a dichotomy, but as a harmonious blend that capitalizes on the strengths of both approaches. Embracing innovative educational practices is seen as instrumental in preparing students for the challenges of the rapidly changing global landscape. This dynamic approach not only enhances the learning experience but also equips students with the skills and adaptability necessary for success in the 21st century. By fostering a synergistic relationship between tradition and innovation, the educational sector endeavors to create a holistic and inclusive framework that empowers learners and cultivates a lifelong love for knowledge and discovery. This transformative journey underscores the commitment to an education system that is both rooted in the richness of tradition and propelled forward by the boundless possibilities of technological advancement.

Keywords. Education, innovation, globalization, information and communication technologies, training.

1 Introduction

As is known, the use of information and communication technologies in the educational process is one of the ways to increase motivation for learning. Information and communication technologies contribute to the development of the creative personality of not only students, but also teachers.

Currently, our country is undergoing significant changes in national education policy. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev noted at a video conference meeting on issues of improving the education and upbringing system,

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accelerating the development of science in the country, education and upbringing are crucial not only in today's life, but also for the future of any state and society. Strengthening the role of education in scientific and technical support for the innovative development of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is confirmed by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated January 28, 2022 No. UP-60 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", the Law "On Education", adopted by the Legislative Chamber on May 19, 2020, approved by the Senate on August 7, 2020, as well as the interest of the Ministry of Public Education and the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in resolving some issues of state policy in the field of scientific and technical support for innovative development of the economy, modernization of the vocational education system, staffing in the field education and science (especially in promising innovative areas), the formation of national research centers, a network of federal and research universities.

One of the main priority directions of state policy in the field of education is the formation of an innovative infrastructure of a system of higher professional education, which provides for the optimization of a network of educational institutions, the organization of innovative resource centers of regional and interregional significance, the integration of universities and manufacturing enterprises, business incubators and other innovative structural units, such as the introduction of dual education.

2 Materials and methods

The process of globalization, which affects many spheres of society, such as political, economic, and cultural, is becoming increasingly significant. Education is no exception. One of the main processes taking place today in the field of education can be called the formation of a common information educational space. It is understood as a set of scientific, educational, cultural and educational institutions (state and non-state, official and unofficial), mass media focused on educational issues and the labor market, the public involved in solving educational problems, as well as socio-psychological stereotypes and attitudes regulating the educational behavior of the population.

3 Results and discussion

In the context of the formation of a new information space in the field of education, traditional education systems are being transformed. New information technologies are used in all forms of educational activities and serve to process, transmit and disseminate information, as well as transform and create new ways of presenting information to students. There is a consolidation and expansion of information educational resources, an increase in the accessibility of education, and the equalization of educational opportunities for subjects of education. The modern educational space is characterized by the spread of information and communication technologies and the technologization of the educational process itself.

Currently, the teacher is not limited in the choice of teaching tools, and the dictates of the times require that teaching be practice-oriented. The expansion of pedagogical methods and techniques, as well as pedagogical innovations, significantly influence the nature of teaching activities. And, accordingly, on students' assimilation of the material. The development of society creates a need for changes even in universal forms of

education. Therefore, in modern practice it is necessary to combine traditional and innovative teaching technologies.

The choice of teaching technology is one of the most important and most difficult elements of teaching activity. When implementing it, one should proceed from the fact that each of the teaching technologies is focused on a certain range of didactic tasks, but does not exclude indirect solutions and other related problems that may have their own technological solution. Therefore, it is necessary to reasonably and creatively evaluate the capabilities of a particular teaching technology, know its strengths and weaknesses, and, on this basis, choose the optimal combination of technologies in relation to the topic of the educational subject and to a specific lesson. In the learning process, it is important to choose general technologies, which are of a specific nature, and private ones, with the help of which learning is carried out as an integral process. The former determine the choice of the latter. The hierarchy of technologies is built for a long time and is implemented in everyday pedagogical work in the form of private technologies and methodological techniques.

It is also necessary to keep in mind that the selection procedure itself and the mechanism for its implementation are very individual and variable. Some teachers, when choosing a teaching technology, primarily proceed from the goal and learning outcomes; others - from the content of the material being studied and its capabilities; others - from the analysis of predicted learning situations, teaching methods, and evidence systems. When implementing the plan, a number of teachers rely primarily on everyday experience with the analysis of options, using pedagogical principles, laws and approaches. However, all teachers who achieve success in their work, when choosing a teaching technology, take into account the following factors:

- leading goals of training and education, as well as specific tasks studying a topic, section;
- the content of the educational lesson, the degree of complexity of the material being studied, its educational and developmental capabilities;
- the level of development of students, their intellectual capabilities;
- the level of basic training of students in the subject, the degree of interest in the material being studied;
- the capabilities and preferences of the teacher, the level of his methodological competence;
- availability of equipment and teaching aids;
- time limit (duration of a training session).

We present approximate stages of making a decision on choosing a teaching technology, an approximate selection algorithm (Table 1).

Table 1. Algorithm for choosing a teaching technology (according to V.I. Zagvyazinsky).

Stage	Contents of teaching activities
1	Awareness or actualization of the goal, general objectives of studying a course, section, topic
2	Analysis of the nature and capabilities of the material being studied. The material is assessed according to different parameters: - according to the level of significance: ideological, general scientific, interdisciplinary, thematic, local; - by nature: theoretical or practical; - by level of complexity: high, medium, low
3	Analysis of the educational capabilities of students: the level of their knowledge and skills, the nature of the accumulated experience, the degree of preparedness and the degree of interest in studying the relevant material
4	Determination of specific objectives of the lesson: educational, including

	developmental, including orientation towards a certain level of activity that needs to be formed (reproductive, algorithmic, productive activity)
5	Making a preliminary decision about the preferred learning technology
6	Adjustment and specification of the decision made, taking into account the available time, funds, equipment, capabilities and preferences of the teacher.

When choosing a teaching technology, it is also necessary to take into account certain conditions based, first of all, on the purpose of studying the section or topic.

1. If the goals of studying a section or topic do not exceed the level of mastery, then reproductive technology of teaching would be quite appropriate, although not the best. It includes: listening carefully to the teacher; students' work with the textbook; observations of the objects and phenomena being studied; performing practical actions according to instructions or prompting from the teacher.

2. If the goals of studying a section or topic are to master the basic algorithms of activity, then the teaching technology should be reproductive-algorithmic. It involves educational and cognitive activities, including taking notes of educational material, giving a report (message), solving standard problems, and participating in didactic games.

3. If the goals of studying a section or topic are aimed at developing experience in search and heuristic activities, then heuristic learning technologies should be chosen, which are dominated by didactic methods using problem-based learning, business games, real design, and analysis of atypical production situations.

4. If the goals of studying a section or topic include the formation of creative technological thinking, then creative teaching technologies are needed, the basis of which are methods of mastering the experience of creative activity; situation of difficult conditions; group solving of creative problems; collective stimulation of creative search ("brainstorming", synthetic; method of morphological analysis and synthesis of technological solutions; functional-cost analysis; method "ARIZ-TRIZ" - theory of solving inventive problems, etc.)

5. If the goals of studying a section or topic are aimed at developing the information culture of students and the ability to process information, then new information technologies should be used: automated teaching systems; interactive programs; multimedia technologies; hypertext technologies; telecommunication projects, etc. The main conditions for the use of educational technologies in practice are: sequence of actions, timeliness of inclusion in the educational process, adequacy to the goals and psychological and pedagogical conditions.

So, when choosing a teaching technology, a teacher is guided by various factors and takes into account various conditions in order to most effectively build the process of students mastering the discipline they teach. Thus, technology is an essential component of the learning process. The teacher's knowledge of the features of various teaching technologies, their adequate application, based on the previously described factors and conditions, will allow for the high-quality organization of the educational process in secondary vocational education. educational institution .

4 Conclusions

Thus, pedagogical technologies are an ordered set of actions, operations and procedures that instrumentally ensure the achievement of a diagnosable and predictable result in the changing conditions of the educational process, using modern technologies. Educational technologies allow the teacher to achieve the planned result, showing innovative skills and instilling interest in each topic.

References

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